

Quantitative proteomic profiling of myoblasts from patients with facioscapulohumeral muscular dystrophy and their unaffected siblings

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Facioscapulohumeral muscular dystrophy (FSHD) affects around 1 in 8000 to 22000 individuals worldwide. The key molecular cause of the disease is the ectopic expression of the double-homeodomain 4 transcription factor (DUX4) that initiates large-scale aberrant gene expression within the muscle cell, resulting in progressive muscle weakness and atrophy. Although gene expression changes have been intensively studied, changes in the proteome in FSHD patients are not established. Here, primary myoblasts (n=2) derived from FSHD patients and their unaffected siblings (UASb) were cultured for 24h. We used label-free LC-MS/MS quantitation to measure protein abundance at baseline and after 24h. A total of 4266 proteins were included in the analysis. On average, protein abundance was not different between groups. However, at the level of individual proteins, 180 exhibited a significant difference in abundance at baseline (P<0.05). Gene ontology revealed the downregulation of RNA binding proteins (heterogeneous and small nuclear ribonucleoproteins) and upregulation of some proteins involved in negative regulators of muscle development: LMCD1 (1.24-fold) and TGFBR2 (1.10-fold). After 24h, 179 proteins were significantly different (P<0.05). FSHD cells were characterized by the downregulation of many E3 ligases such as E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase DTX3L (1.6-fold), and proteasomal subunits (PSMA5, PSMB4, PSMC1, and PSME2). Surprisingly, some E3 ligases (TRIM38, XIAP and PPP1R11) upregulated at the same time with a role in regulating the degradation of immune system proteins such as TRL2 and IFNB1. These results provide a progression toward establishing proteome changes in FSHD patients and valuable resources for potential therapeutic targets.

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